

SHORTER NOTE

High phenotypic variation of *Struthiopteris spicant* (Blechnaceae) at the edge of its

range.— Phenotypic variation may be due to genetic and/or environmental causes.

Phenotypic plasticity can be defined as a change in the phenotype that is expressed by a single genotype when subjected to different environments (Gratani, *Advances in Botany* 208747:17 pp. 2014). Despite long debate (Ghalambor *et al.*, *Functional Ecology* 21:394–407. 2007), many ecologists consider phenotypic plasticity as to be an evolutionary strategy for adapting to variable environments, because individuals sense environmental cues in early life stages and express phenotypes that have higher fitness in conditions found later in life (Xue and Leibler, *Proceedings of the National Academy of Sciences, USA* 115:12745–12750. 2018). In addition, it has been hypothesized that plasticity is more pronounced at the edge of the range of a species or in peripheral populations because they are exposed to high environmental variation where plastic genotypes can be advantageous (Valladares *et al.*, *Ecology Letters* 17:1351–1364. 2014). However, in seed plants, there is experimental evidence both for (*e.g.*, Lázaro-Nogal *et al.*, *Journal of Ecology* 103:338–350. 2015) and against (*e.g.*, Berg, Becker and Matthies, *Oecologia* 143:220–231. 2005) this prediction. As far as we know, this hypothesis has not been tested in ferns, but several studies have analyzed the adaptive significance of phenotypic plasticity in leaf form and function (*e.g.*, Saldaña, Gianoli and Lusk, *Oecologia* 145:252–257. 2005; Rünk and Zobel, *Plant Ecology* 193:85–99. 2007).

A special case of leaf plasticity is represented by dimorphism, the ability to produce different sterile and fertile leaves. Dimorphic ferns show reduced laminar area in some part (typically the apex) or in the entire fertile leaf relative to the sterile leaf (Wagner and Wagner, *Gardens' Bulletin, Singapore* 30:251–267. 1977; Watkins, Churchill, and Holbrook, *American Journal of Botany* 103:845–855. 2016). Although dimorphism has repeatedly

evolved in distinct fern lineages and is present in many species, only rarely has its evolutionary significance been studied (Watkins, Churchill, and Holbrook, 2016). Britton and Watkins (Annals of Botany 118:1139–1149. 2016) concluded that this functional specialization is an adaptation to increase spore dispersal distance and/or spore production, which offsets the costs of photosynthetic decrease due to reduction in photosynthetically active tissues, especially in resource-rich environments.

Struthiopteris spicant (L.) Weiss (Blechnaceae) is a terrestrial or saxicolous fern with markedly dimorphic leaves: the fertile leaves are erect, longer than the sterile, and present heavily contracted pinnae, which have costal sori protected by continuous indusia (Rolleri and Prada, Acta Botanica Malacitana 31:7–50. 2006). In Europe, there are two varieties of this species, var. *pradae* S. Molino & Gabriel y Galán (Molino *et al.*, Plant Systematics and Evolution 305:255–268. 2019), and var. *homophyllum* (Merino) Gabriel y Galán & R. Pino (Wasowicz, Gabriel y Galán, and Pino, Phytotaxa 302:198–200. 2017), which show partial or almost complete reversal of dimorphism, respectively (Fig. 1). The var. *homophyllum* comprises small plants, with erect leaves up to 20 cm, usually all sporogenous. Fertile leaves can produce sporangia along all their length, from base to apex, on slightly contracted pinnae, and the sori are typically fragmented, with discontinuous indusia (Fig. 1A). The var. *pradae* is similar in size to the typical variety, but with two distinct types of fertile leaves on the same individual simultaneously: some similar to the typical “fertile *spicant*” leaf, and others more similar to typical “sterile *spicant*”, *i.e.* non-contracted, but at least partially sporogenous and with interrupted sori and indusia (Fig. 1C).

Struthiopteris spicant has a wide circumboreal distribution (Fig. 2A), occurring in the Pacific Northwest area of North America (USA: California, Oregon, Washington, Alaska; Canada: British Columbia), throughout central and western Europe (from Sweden, Poland, Ukraine, and Romania westwards to Iceland and the Iberian Peninsula), some parts of northern Africa

(where it is rare), and the Macaronesian archipelagos (Canary Islands, Madeira, and Azores Islands). Until now, the varieties *homophyllum* and *pradae* were known only from north of the Iberian Peninsula, which is the southern edge of the European range of *S. spicant* (Fig. 2B). We discovered new locations of both varieties (marked by * in the Appendix), which extend their known distributions beyond this peripheral area in mainland Europe as well as in some Macaronesian islands (S. Miguel and Madeira, which are, respectively, 1500 and 1200 km from the nearest Iberian locations; Figs. 2B, 2C, 2D). In many of these locations, we also observed individuals of var. *spicant* and individuals with intermediate phenotype between this variety and the other variety present there (*homophyllum* or *pradae*; Figs. 1B, 1D). To assess the morphological variation of these populations, we studied two characters, fertile leaf length and cenosori coverage, in a large sample (43 individuals listed in Appendix). We measured the longest fertile leaf of each individual, and cenosori coverage (%) as the portion of the length of all pinnae of a lamina covered by cenosori (Fig. 1). These lengths were obtained on scanned images of leaves with the program ImageJ (Abramoff, Magalhaes, and Ram, *Biophotonics International* 11:36–42. 2004). For cenosori coverage, we randomly selected one fertile leaf from each individual, of non-contracted type in the cases of var. *pradae* and in intermediate individuals between this variety and var. *spicant*. We analyzed both variables by one-factor ANOVA, with variety as fixed factor, and Tukey tests for subsequent pairwise comparisons. Cenosori coverage was arcsine transformed to improve normality.

The three varieties differed both in fertile leaf length (ANOVA: $F_{2,26} = 20.14$, $P < 0.0001$) and cenosori coverage ($F_{2,26} = 53.42$, $P < 0.0001$). Fertile leaves of var. *spicant* (mean \pm SE: 45.2 ± 3.9 cm) and *pradae* (34.5 ± 4.8 cm) were similar (Tukey test: $P > 0.05$), whereas those of var. *homophyllum* (13.3 ± 1.9 cm) were significantly shorter (Fig. 3). Cenosori coverage decreased significantly (Tukey tests: $P < 0.05$) in the order var. *spicant*

($93.7 \pm 1.3 \%$) > var. *homophyllum* ($50.2 \pm 4.8 \%$) > var. *pradae* ($30.1 \pm 5.2 \%$). Both characters were highly variable between individuals of each variety, as shown by the high standard errors, and the individuals with intermediate phenotype further widened these ranges of variation (Fig. 3). Our observational data thus give some support to the hypothesis of increased phenotypic plasticity in populations at the edge of ranges. For instance, the populations in the Iberian Peninsula are under a Mediterranean climate, with a higher seasonal and between-year variation in precipitation than those occurring in the main species distribution (Mosmann *et al.*, Atmospheric Research 70:43–53. 2004). This should favor plastic genotypes, but to properly address phenotypic plasticity, experimental studies with replicated genotypes are needed, *i.e.*, clonal individuals or individuals with known genetic relatedness (Gianoli and Valladares, Biological Journal of the Linnean Society 105:1–7. 2012). In fact, *S. spicant* populations from the Iberian Peninsula have high genetic variation (Peredo *et al.*, American Fern Journal 103:27–39. 2013), which may also explain their phenotypic variation.

Interestingly, we found the majority of small, almost monomorphic individuals (*i.e.*, var. *homophyllum*) on steep slopes with skeletal soils. Water and nutrient availability in this habitat are lower than in forest understories, the typical habitat of var. *spicant*. Thus, this observation is consistent with the positive association between leaf dimorphism and resource-rich habitats (Britton and Watkins, 2016). Because fertile leaves of dimorphic individuals (var. *spicant*) are more upright and longer than sterile leaves, their spores should disperse at greater distances. The fertile pinnae also have a greater proportion of their length covered by sori than those of monomorphic individuals, which allows greater spore production in the var. *spicant*. However, under poor growth conditions, these advantages do not compensate for photosynthetic costs, because of reduced lamina area. Common garden or

transplant experiments will be required to assess the relative contributions of environmental and genetic factors for the observed phenotype variation.

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APPENDIX

List of plant material.— (New collections of the varieties *homophyllum* and *pradae* are identified with *; vouchers deposited in the herbarium MA - Real Jardín Botánico de Madrid, Spain).

Struthiopteris spicant var. **homophyllum** (Merino) Gabriel y Galán & R.Pino. PORTUGAL. Azores: San Miguel Island, Algarvia, *L.G. Quintanilla*, 17 Mar 2007, MA 939454*; Trilhos Novos, *L.G. Quintanilla*, 16 Mar 2007, MA 939453*. Braga: Vieira do Minho, *Prada*, 1 Oct 2004, MACB 109621. Madeira Island: ER228 road between Encumeada and S. Vicente, *L.G. Quintanilla*, 02 May 1998, MA 939455*. SPAIN. A Coruña: A Baña, San Mamede de Monte church, *L.G. Quintanilla*, 13 Aug 2004, MA 939457*; Mariaqueira river, *L.G. Quintanilla*, 21 Feb 2001, MA 939456*; Santiago, Cantaleta, *Barrera*, 29 Jul 1967, MACB 32367. Pontevedra: between Tabagón and Tomiño, *Gabriel y Galán*, 19 Mar 2016, MACB 109617; Mondariz, *Gabriel y Galán*, 20 Mar 2016, MACB 109618. Salamanca: Batuecas, *Gabriel y Galán*, 15 May 2016, MACB 109626. **S. spicant** intermediate between var. **homophyllum** and var. **spicant**. PORTUGAL. Madeira Island: ER228 road between Encumeada and S. Vicente, *L.G. Quintanilla*, 2 May 1998, MACB 113888, MACB 113887, MACB 1138890, MACB 113887. SPAIN. Canary Islands: Tenerife, Anaga Mountains, *A. Santos*, 25 Oct 1989, MACB 483040. Pontevedra: Mondariz, *Gabriel y Galán*, 20 May 2016, MACB 113881, MACB113883, MACB 113884; Redondela, *I. Barrera*, 1 Nov 1976, MACB 004769. **S. spicant** var. **pradae** S.Molino & Gabriel y Galán. SPAIN. Asturias: Valdés, Paladeporre, *Gabriel y Galán*, 22 Mar 2016, MACB 109613, MACB 109615; Luarca, *Gabriel y Galán*, 26 Jul 2017, MACB 110660; Otur, *Gabriel y Galán*, 17 Aug 2017, MACB 110661. Burgos: San Millán range, *Fuentes*, 27 Sep 1975, MACB 5994. Zamora: Aciberos, *Molino & al.*, 23 Sep 2017, MACB 110654. León: Hayedo de Busmayor, *R. Vázquez*, 19 Jun 2019, MA 939449*; Pinar de Lillo, *R. Vázquez*, 20 Jun 2019, MA 939450*. Madrid: Rascafría, trail near Pradillo dam, *S. Molino et al.*, 24 Feb 2019, MA 939451*. Navarra: Belagua, towards Lapatia pass,

J.M. Gabriel y Galán & M. Puelles, 26 Aug 2019, MA 939452*. **S. spicant** intermediate between var. **pradae** and var. **spicant**. SPAIN. Asturias: Castañedo, *Molino et al.*, 20 Sep 2017, MACB 113877; Otur, *Gabriel y Galán*, 19 Jul 2017, MACB 113876, MACB 113879, MACB 113880. Zamora: Aciberos, *Molino et al.*, 23 Sep 2017, MACB 113878. **S. spicant** var. **spicant**. BELGIUM. Turnhout: Engels Kamp, *W. van Cotthem*, 18 Jun 1973, MA 809713. DENMARK. Faurhult Heat near Frederikshaun, *Lars Jensen et al.*, 26 Jul 1968, MA 213361. FRANCE. Autriche, Tyrol, Alpes du Stubai, *D. Podlech*, 18 Aug 1986, MA 464909. PORTUGAL. Azores: S. Miguel Island, Furnas, Terra Nostra Park, *J.A. Ramos & L.G. Quintanilla*, 17 Mar 2007, MACB 113885. SPAIN. Basque Country: Álava, Ulibarri Olleros, El Portucho, *P.M. Uribe-Echevarría*, 10 Oct 1987, MACB 030899. Cantabria: Camaleño, Cosgaya, *Gabriel y Galán*, 1 Oct 2016, MACB 109622. A Coruña: Monfero, Caaveiro, *S. González Crespo*, 18 Oct 1986, MACB 031064. Lugo: Murás, Puente Rioboo, *F.J. Silva Pando et al.*, 2 Aug 1987, MACB 030875.

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FIG. 1. Representative plants of *Struthiopteris spicant* used in this study. A. Var. *homophyllum* (MA939455). B. Individual intermediate between var. *homophyllum* and var. *spicant* (MACB004769). C. Var. *pradae* (MA939452). D. Individual intermediate between var. *pradae* and var. *spicant* (MACB113878). The four individuals are shown at the same scale. In each individual, an example of each type of leaf is labeled: s, sterile; fc, fertile contracted; fn, fertile non-contracted. The detail shows abaxial surface of medial pinnae, with portions covered (orange lines) or not covered (blue lines) by cenosori.

FIG. 2. Distribution of *Struthiopteris spicant* and its Iberian-Macaronesian varieties. A. World distribution of *Struthiopteris spicant*, showing two disjunct centers: Western North America and Central-Western Europe/Macaronesia. B-D. Distributional details in the Iberian Peninsula (B), and Macaronesia: Azores Islands (C) and Madeira/Canary Islands (D). (Source of data of general distribution of *Struthiopteris spicant*: GBIF Secretariat (2019). GBIF Backbone Taxonomy. Checklist dataset <https://www.gbif.org/species/9271606> accessed via GBIF.org on 2019-12-07).

FIG. 3. Variability of two characters of fertile leaves among varieties of *Struthiopteris spicant*. Each dot corresponds to one individual. *homophyllum-spicant* and *pradae-spicant* are individuals with intermediate phenotype between var. *spicant* and var. *homophyllum* or var. *pradae*, respectively.